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Genes associated with aging in the hematopoietic system in humans.

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We provide here the first systems biologic dissection of genes important for the aging process in Homo sapiens in the hematopoietic compartment.

Results

The genes identified and described here were either important for the aging process themselves or were of importance to the study and description of aging in humans because their expression denoted a separate developmental stage marked by age.

1. Interferon stimulated genes

- a. IFIT2 (aged)
- b. IFIT1 (aged)
- c. MND A (aged)
- d. IFITM10, IFI27L1, ISG20 and IRGM were instead associated with young HSC.
- e. Ifngr1 and ifnar1 (young)
- f. Irf7 (young)
- g. Ifngr2 (age)
- h. Irf3 (young)

2. Imprinting associated genes

- a. KHDRBS3 (young)
- b. ATRX (aged)
- c. ILF3 (young)
- d. KHDC
- e. DZIP1 (young)
- f. BRWD1-IT2 (young)

3. PDCD

- a. PDCD2 (young)
- b. PDCD2L (age)
- c. PDCD4-AS1 (young)

4. VEGF family factors are expressed higher in young HSC.

5. Leupaxin (young)

6. PRC1 switch

- a. RYBP
- b. PCGF5 was induced with age
- c. PCGF3 (young)

7. Caspase induction during aging

- a. Casp10 induction
- b. Casp9 silencing
- c. CASP7 induction

8. FGF family growth factors

- a. FGF20 (age)
- b. FGF18 (young)

- 1 9. CSF2RB induction
- 2 10. CMC4 (young)
- 3 11. Co receptors of the immune system
- 4 a. Cd274 induction
- 5 b. CD9 (youth)
- 6 12. Angiopoietin System
- 7 a. Only angiopoietin 2, ANGPT2, was associated with youth
- 8 b. AMOTL1/2 and ANGPT1 were instead associated with aging.
- 9 13. Mboat7 (aging)
- 10 14. MIF
- 11 15. GDF family
- 12 a. GDF11 (young)
- 13 b. GDF5 (young)
- 14 c. GDF1 (was a mixed transcript)
- 15 16. LOC101927647
- 16 17. The proliferation program and transformation
- 17 a. MBD3L1 (youth)
- 18 b. PAX8-AS1 (age)
- 19 c. Top2A (age)
- 20 d. CDK6 (youth)
- 21 e. TK1 (young)
- 22 18. Butyrophilins
- 23 a. BTN2A1
- 24 b. BTN3A3 (age)
- 25 19. Self antigens
- 26 a. HCG18 (young)
- 27 b. Plac8 (young)
- 28 c. RhD (age)
- d. RhBG (young)
- e. GYPA (age)
- f. Stim2 (age)
- g. STIM1 (youth)
- h. STAG3L4
20. Immunoglobulin-like receptors
- a. LRFN4 (young)
- b. FNDC4 (aged)
- c. LRRTM2 (young)

- 1 21. PRSS genes
- 2 a. PRSS53
- 3 22. Growth factors signaling
- 4 a. IGFBP7 (young)
- 5 23. Adrenomedullin 5 is expressed in young HSC.
- 6 24. Nutrient sensing
- 7 a. Vps13b (aged)
- 8 b. Sestrin 2 (youth)
- 9 c. Akt3 (age)
- 10 d. Fkbp8 (youth)
- 11 e. Vps28 (youth)
- 12 f. TSC2 (age)
- 13 g. Tsc22d4 (age)
- 14 h. Tsc22d3 (young)
- 15 25. Metabolism
- 16 a. H6PD (young)
- 17 b. HMGCR (age)
- 18 c. DOHH (young)
- 19 d. TDH (young)
- 20 e. IDH3A (age)
- 21 f. D2HGDH (youth)
- 22 g. HIBCH (age)
- 23 h. IDNK (age)
- 24 26. Epigenetic machinery
- 25 a. MBD4 (age)
- 26 b. BRD2 (young)
- 27 c. KMT2A
- 28 d. Phf7 (young)
- e. Brd4 (youth)
- 27 27. Glucocorticoid signaling
- 28 28. Complement system
- a. CR1
- 29 29. Cytochrome genes
- a. POR
- 30 30. Olfactory system in young and aged HSC
- a. OR1G1 (youth)
- b. OR1C1 (young)
- c. OR2H1 (young)
- d. OR10J1 (age)

- 1 31. Membrane genes
- 2 a. SMIM12 (youth)
- 3 b. SMIM14
- 4 32. MFSD14B is a marker of aging in the hematopoietic system.
- 5 33. Major facilitator genes in the HSC are associated with aging
- 6 a. Mfsd10 (young)
- 7 b. Mfsd4b (age)
- 8 c. Mfsd6l (young)
- 9 34. TNF superfamily receptors and ligands in young and aged HSC.
- 10 a. TNFSF10 (aged)
- 11 b. TNFSF14 (age)
- 12 c. TNFSF4 (age)
- 13 35. Nucleotide synthesis
- 14 a. UMPS (age)
- 15 36. Stromal derived factor 4 is preferentially expressed in young HSC.
- 16 37. FSHR is preferentially expressed in young HSC.
- 17 38. Prostaglandin and arachidonate biosynthesis is associated with aging in humans.
- 18 a. PTGS1
- 19 b. COX15
- 20 c. COX
- 21 d. ALOXE3 (young)
- 22 e. Ltb4r2 (young)
- 23 39. Antibacterial effectors and aging.
- 24 a. Mblac2
- 25 b. Leap2
- 26 40. PDCD2 in young HSC.
- 27 41. RNA interference in aging in the HSC.
- 28 a. DICER1
- 29 b. Ago4
- 30 42. Nuclear transport and the NPC
- 31 a. Nup58 (young)
- 32 b. LMNA
- 33 c. NARFL(young)
- 34 d. LBR (age)
- 35 43. CSF3R marks young HSCs.
- 36 a. Csf2
- 37 44. IL1R1 and IL1RAP (young)

- 1 45. CARD19
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- 3 46. Thrombosis genes
- 4 a. PTAFR activation
- 5 b. VWDE (age)
- 6
- 7 47. Nocturnin (youth)
- 8
- 9 48. NCDN (age)
- 10
- 11 49. Neurotrophic factors and neuropeptides
- 12 a. NPFF (age)
- 13 b. NENF (youth)
- 14 c. GIPR (youth)
- 15 d. VIPR2
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- 17 50. Lactotransferrin increases with age.
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- 19 51. Aged HSC express frataxin.
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- 21 52. MET is associated with youth in the HSC.
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- 23 53. GSK3A in young HSC.
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- 25 54. KL in aged HSC.
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- 27 55. FAAP20 in aged HSC.
- 28 a. FAAP100 was instead expressed in young HSC.
56. ABCA5 is expressed in aged HSC.
57. SIGIRR distinguishes young and aged HSC.
58. PIWIL4 (aged)
59. Iron transport
- a. HFE
60. KLF factors are associated with youth in HSC.
- a. KLF8 (youth)
- b. KLF7 (youth)
- c. KLF2
- d. KLF5 specifically marked aged HSC
61. NPR2 (aged)
62. FPR3 (age)
63. Ataxin-1 (age)
64. DCXR and TECR are associated with an aging-specific biological function in human HSC.

- 1 65. Steroid biosynthesis
- 2 a. AKR1C1 (youth)
- 3 66. MicroRNAs that distinguish young and aged HSC in humans.
- 4 a. miR-10A
- 5 b. miR-99AHG (young)
- 6 c. miR-210HG (young)
- 7 67. RIP kinase in the HSC is associated with aging in humans.
- 8 a. RIPK2
- 9 68. Junctional composition is a signature difference between the HSC in young and aged humans.
- 10 69. CDH7 marks aged HSC.
- 11 70. DLX homeobox factors are associated with aging in human HSC.
- 12 a. DLX6
- 13 b. DLX5
- 14 c. DLX4
- 15 d. DLX2
- 16 e. DLX1
- 17 71. Ep400 is preferentially expressed in young HSC.
- 18 72. TTC profiling of the HSC through lifetime.
- 19 a. TTC5 (age)
- 20 b. Ttc7b (age)
- 21 c. Ttc26 marked aged HSC
- 22 d. Ttc30 and TTC38 marked young HSC
- 23 73. ERBB4 is expressed preferentially in young HSC.
- 24 74. HPGDS
- 25 75. Pou2f2 and Sall4
- 26 76. Hsh2d
- 27 77. Hymai
- 28 78. Hemopexin
79. Ccl25
80. Cxcl6 (age)
81. Cxcl3 (youth)
82. Ccl25 (youth)
83. Ccr2 (age)
84. APP increases with age in the HSC.

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85. IKZF family genes are associated with aging in the HSC

a. IKZF4 (age)

86. Azuricidin

87. Aftiphilin

88. ACKR receptors in the young and aged HSC

a. ACKR2

b. ACKR3

89. PRR family genes

a. PRR14 And PRRC2A (youth)

b. PRR5L and PRR16 (age)

90. CYR61 marks the HSC in youth.

91. Gprin2 marks young HSC.